

Introduction

Sheep production remains a crucial component of smallholder agriculture in India, providing meat, skins, and income for marginal farmers and landless labourers. Mecheri sheep, a native hair breed from Tamil Nadu, are renowned for their good carcass yield, quality skin, and rapid growth (Balasundaram et al., 2023). Despite increasing demand for red meat, low growth rates, variable feed conversion, and reproductive inefficiencies constrain profitability (Satish Kumar et al., 2018). Growth rate and feed efficiency, typically measured through average daily gain (ADG) and Kleiber ratio (KR), are vital economic traits (Fitzhugh and Taylor, 1971; Kleiber, 1947). KR is particularly advantageous since it eliminates the need for individual feed intake measurement (Scholtz and Roux, 1988). Recent studies persist in highlighting KR's efficacy in sheep breeding within low-input systems (Besufkad et al., 2024; Dash et al., 2025). Understanding how non-genetic factors influence these traits is vital to refine breeding strategies and improve selection accuracy (Salman et al., 2024; Schaub et al., 2025).

Materials and Methods

Data

Data spanning 1979–2018 from the Mecheri Sheep Research Station (MSRS), Tamil Nadu, were evaluated. Lambs suckled for three months, got creep feed starting in week two, and were weaned at three months. Post-weaning, they grazed for 7–8 hours daily and received concentrate supplementation. Controlled mating made that the pedigree was correct, and the weights of the lambs were taken at birth, weaning, six months, nine months, and one year. The majority of ewes were culled at ages six to seven, depending on their condition. The average body weight measurements of lambs at various stages—birth (BW), weaning (WW), six months (6MW), nine months (9MW), and yearling (12MW)—were recorded as 2.35, 9.76, 13.72, 16.68, and 19.46 kg, respectively. Following the removal of outliers, a dataset comprising growth information for 2,616 lambs, along with their pedigree details, was established. These lambs were produced with the contributions of 226 sires and 1,044 dams (Table 1). The mean number of records per ewe varied from 1.59 for yearlings (12MW) to 2.50 at birth (BW), while rams demonstrated values ranging from 6.36 for yearlings (12MW) to 11.57 at birth (BW).

Table 1. Description of Mecheri sheep for ADG and KR traits

Trait	Number of lambs	No. of sires	No. of dams	Mean	Coefficient of variation (%)
ADG1	2286	208	961	80.57 g	30.25
ADG2	1578	183	814	42.54 g	47.40
ADG3	1203	167	701	33.13 g	57.17
ADG4	1019	160	638	29.83 g	66.08
KR1	2286	208	961	14.42	13.63
KR2	1578	183	814	6.03	42.36
KR3	1203	167	701	4.01	53.24
KR4	1019	160	638	3.21	62.80

ADG1 to ADG4 and KR1 to KR4 - Average daily weight gains and Kleiber ratios for the growth intervals 0-3, 3-6, 6-9 and 9-12 months.

Data analysis

Growth efficiency traits, specifically average daily weight gain (ADG) and the Kleiber ratio (KR), were calculated based on the body weight characteristics of lambs. ADG is defined as the variation in body weight over a designated time period (Fitzhugh and Taylor, 1971).

$$\text{ADG} = (y_{t_2} - y_{t_1}) / (t_2 - t_1)$$

Where, y_{t_1} and y_{t_2} are the body weights at t_1 and t_2 ages in days, respectively. In this investigation, the pre-weaning ADG or ADG1 (birth to 3-months) and post-weaning ADGs namely, ADG2 (3-6 months), ADG3 (6-9 months), ADG4 (9-12 months) were studied. Kleiber ratio (KR) is the proportion of average daily weight gain to the metabolic body weight ($W^{0.75}$) (Kleiber, 1947).

$$\text{KR} = \text{ADG}/\text{WT}^{0.75}$$

Where, ADG is the average daily weight gain for the period expressed in g/day and $W^{0.75}$ is the metabolic body weight at the later age of the growth period for which Kleiber ratio is calculated. Four number of KR values were calculated for different growth periods namely, KR1 (pre-weaning), KR2 (3-6 months), KR3 (6-9 months) and KR4 (9-12 months).

The lambs were classified according to non-genetic factors, including sex (male and female), season of birth (main and off), birth period (1980-1984, 1985-1989, 1990-1994, 1995-1999, 2000-2004, 2005-2008, 2009-2013, and 2014-2018), type of birth (single and twin), and ewe parity (parity -1, 2, 3, and parity 4 and above). All non-genetic factors were treated as fixed effects, while the dam's weight during lambing was included as a covariate in the statistical analysis. A series of least-squares studies were conducted on growth efficiency traits using a general linear model to evaluate the impact of various non-genetic factors on growth traits.

$$Y_{ijklmn} = \mu + P_i + C_j + D_k + S_l + B_m + e_{ijklmn}$$

where, Y_{ijklmn} , and e_{ijklmn} are the lamb's growth efficiency trait (ADG or KR), overall mean for

the trait and random error associated with each observation, respectively. The effect of non-genetic factors, period of birth, season of birth, parity of dam, sex of lamb and type of birth are mentioned in the model as P_i , C_j , D_k , S_l and B_m , respectively.

Results and Discussion

Average daily weight gain

The performances of Mecheri sheep with respect to average daily weight gain (ADG) and Kleiber ratio (KR) traits are presented in Tables 2 and 3. The mean least-squares estimates for ADG1, ADG2, ADG3, and ADG4 were 81.83, 42.14, 32.83, and 30.58 g/day, respectively. Growth peaked during the pre-weaning phase (birth to 3 months) and subsequently diminished. This pattern illustrates the nutritional benefits of dam's milk and the genetic inclination for accelerated early growth. Post-weaning, weight increase increasingly relied on grazing resources, and the noted reduction in average daily gain may be linked to competition for feed and grazing stress (Mahala et al., 2019). Comparable decreasing tendencies with age have been documented in several breeds, including Nilagiri, Madras Red, Deccani, and Nellore sheep (Devendran et al., 2010; Ganesan et al., 2015; Satish Kumar et al., 2017; Bhakthavatchalam, 2019; Mahala et al., 2020).

The pre-weaning average daily gain (ADG) recorded in this study surpassed earlier findings for Mecheri sheep (Thiruvankadan et al., 2011; Jeichitra and Rajendran, 2013) and was comparable to that of Nilagiri (Panneerselvam, 1993; Venkataramanan et al., 2015) and Madras Red breeds (Devendran et al., 2010; Ganesan et al., 2015). Nevertheless, elevated pre-weaning gains were documented in Madras Red (Balasubramanyam and Kumarasamy, 2011), Nellore (Satish Kumar et al., 2017; Bhakthavatchalam, 2019), and Deccani sheep (Dasari, 2017). The post-weaning average daily

gains ADG2 (3–6 months) and ADG4 (9–12 months) in this study surpassed earlier Mecheri estimates, although ADG3 (6–9 months) was marginally lower (Jeichitra and Rajendran, 2013). Values were broadly comparable to those of Nilagiri sheep (Venkataramanan et al., 2015), although ADG4 in Mecheri was superior.

The period of birth significantly affected all ADG features, with elevated values noted from 2000–2018. This enhancement may be ascribed to genetic advancements, superior management practices, and advantageous environmental conditions over time. These results align with studies conducted on Nilagiri, Mecheri, Madras Red, Nellore, and Avikalin breeds (Panneerselvam, 1993; Ganesan et al., 2015; Venkataramanan et al., 2015; Jeichitra et al., 2016; Satish Kumar et al., 2017; Bhakthavatchalam, 2019). Recent genomic research underscores the necessity of considering environmental variations across decades when analysing genetic trends in growth characteristics (Schaub et al., 2025).

The season of birth had a significant effect on ADG1, ADG3, and ADG4, but not on ADG2. Lambs born during the off-season demonstrated markedly superior pre-weaning weight growth compared to those born in the primary season. This is probably attributable to reduced flock density, increased resource availability, and superior maternal nutrition during gestation, leading to enhanced milk production. Seasonal climate variability, particularly in forage

availability, may also explain fluctuations in growth performance (Balasubramanyam and Kumarasamy, 2011; Ganesan et al., 2015; Jeichitra et al., 2016; Satish Kumar et al., 2018; Bhakthavatchalam, 2019). These results align with recent findings that environmental seasonality has a major effect on early growth trajectories in small ruminants (Heinzen et al., 2023; Salman et al., 2024).

The body weight of the dam at lambing significantly influenced pre-weaning growth (ADG1), underscoring the importance of maternal condition during gestation. Since dam body condition directly affects milk production and neonatal growth, optimal nutrition before lambing is essential for maximizing lamb performance. Ren et al. (2024) reached a comparable outcome, indicating substantial maternal influences on early growth characteristics in Luzhong sheep.

Sex exerted no substantial influence on ADG characteristics, with the exception of ADG4, in which males demonstrated much greater gains than females. This disparity may be ascribed to endocrine and metabolic variations between genders that become increasingly evident with advancing age (Swenson and Reece, 1993). Similar sex effects on late-stage growth have been noted in many Indian sheep breeds (Devendran et al., 2007; Venkataramanan et al., 2015; Jeichitra et al., 2016; Bhakthavatchalam, 2019).

Table 2. Least-squares means (\pm SE) for ADG traits of Mecheri sheep

Effect	ADG1 (g)	ADG2 (g)	ADG3 (g)	ADG4 (g)
Overall	81.83 \pm 0.72 (2286)	42.14 \pm 0.81 (1578)	32.83 \pm 0.82 (1203)	30.58 \pm 0.93 (1019)
Sex	NS	NS	NS	*
Male	82.72 \pm 0.96 (1212)	46.05 \pm 1.20 (682)	37.43 \pm 1.28 (469)	35.64 ^a \pm 1.48 (352)
Female	80.93 \pm 1.08 (1074)	38.31 \pm 1.09 (896)	28.41 \pm 1.03 (734)	25.82 ^b \pm 1.16 (667)
Period	**	**	**	**
1980-1984	80.28 ^c \pm 1.47 (255)	32.42 ^a \pm 1.77 (172)	19.86 ^a \pm 1.82 (147)	33.72 ^{bc} \pm 2.26 (123)
1985-1989	60.12 ^a \pm 2.83	49.49 ^d \pm 3.17	27.29 ^{ab} \pm 3.11	37.29 ^{bc} \pm 3.23

	(141)	(104)	(77)	(75)
1990-1994	65.42 ^a ± 1.56 (156)	41.80 ^{bc} ± 1.60 (134)	33.82 ^a ± 1.61 (120)	27.79 ^b ± 1.83 (97)
1995-1999	69.54 ^{ab} ± 2.47 (151)	32.29 ^{ab} ± 2.47 (127)	35.30 ^{cd} ± 1.76 (100)	26.25 ^b ± 2.18 (74)
2000-2004	72.52 ^b ± 1.84 (266)	55.43 ^d ± 1.84 (253)	36.33 ^c ± 2.00 (196)	18.75 ^a ± 2.45 (158)
2005-2008	82.90 ^c ± 1.66 (596)	41.39 ^c ± 1.70 (449)	36.20 ^d ± 1.66 (389)	37.51 ^c ± 1.77 (345)
2009-2013	95.53 ^d ± 1.76 (558)	38.64 ^b ± 2.08 (300)	38.22 ^{cd} ± 2.59 (146)	33.08 ^{bc} ± 2.91 (127)
2014-2018	93.82 ^d ± 2.44 (163)	47.99 ^{cd} ± 3.62 (39)	34.55 ^{bcd} ± 3.70 (28)	28.60 ^{abc} ± 4.27 (20)
Season	**	NS	*	**
Main	74.25 ^a ± 0.71 (1572)	43.91 ± 0.79 (1161)	34.70 ^b ± 0.87 (899)	28.23 ^a ± 0.99 (750)
Off	91.40 ^b ± 1.37 (714)	39.72 ± 1.50 (417)	29.73 ^a ± 1.61 (304)	34.39 ^b ± 1.84 (269)
Type of birth	NS	NS	NS	NS
Single	79.49 ± 0.62 (2257)	42.88 ± 0.75 (1569)	32.57 ± 0.78 (1200)	30.43 ± 0.91 (1016)
Twin	98.14 ± 3.84 (29)	31.60 ± 6.20 (9)	40.84 ± 9.74 (3)	35.37 ± 10.06 (3)
Parity	NS	NS	NS	NS
1	80.56 ± 1.31 (786)	40.41 ± 1.41 (564)	32.25 ± 1.40 (435)	30.55 ± 1.80 (351)
2	80.92 ± 1.51 (594)	42.56 ± 1.43 (405)	30.77 ± 1.60 (311)	31.65 ± 1.83 (268)
3	83.96 ± 1.38 (440)	43.88 ± 1.72 (329)	31.41 ± 1.67 (266)	30.13 ± 1.76 (232)
4 and above	82.11 ± 1.66 (466)	41.78 ± 1.94 (280)	37.18 ± 1.91 (191)	29.91 ± 2.12 (168)
Body weight of dam at lambing	**	NS	NS	NS
** P<0.01; *P<0.05; NS – Not significant; Subclass means with dissimilar superscripts are significantly different from each other; Figure in parenthesis indicates number of observations.				

Table 3. Least-squares means (± SE) for Kleiber ratio traits in Mecheri sheep

Effect	KR1	KR2	KR3	KR4
Overall	14.55 ± 0.06 (2286)	5.84 ± 0.09 (1578)	3.90 ± 0.09 (1203)	3.23 ± 0.09 (1019)
Sex	NS	NS	NS	NS
Male	14.55 ± 0.08 (1212)	6.18 ± 0.14 (682)	4.29 ± 0.14 (469)	3.61 ± 0.15 (352)
Female	14.56 ± 0.09 (1074)	5.50 ± 0.13 (896)	3.51 ± 0.11 (734)	2.88 ± 0.1 (667)
Period	**	**	**	**
1980-1984	14.43 ^c ± 0.13 (255)	4.59 ^a ± 0.21 (172)	2.48 ^a ± 0.20 (147)	3.69 ^{b±} 0.23 (123)
1985-1989	12.75 ^a ± 0.25 (141)	7.36 ^c ± 0.38 (104)	3.52 ^{ab} ± 0.35 (77)	4.07 ^{b±} 0.33 (75)

1990-1994	13.11 ^{ab} ± 0.14 (156)	6.32 ^b ± 0.19 (134)	4.32 ^{bcd} ± 0.18 (120)	3.18 ^b ± 0.19 (97)
1995-1999	13.53 ^a ± 0.22 (151)	4.93 ^b ± 0.29 (127)	4.54 ^{cd} ± 0.19 (100)	3.01 ^b ± 0.22 (74)
2000-2004	13.67 ^b ± 0.16 (266)	7.63 ^c ± 0.22 (253)	4.26 ^{c±} 0.22 (196)	2.03 ^a ± 0.25 (158)
2005-2008	14.82 ^c ± 0.14 (596)	5.82 ^b ± 0.20 (449)	4.23 ^{bd} ± 0.18 (389)	3.82 ^b ± 0.18 (345)
2009-2013	15.87 ^{d±} 0.15 (558)	5.00 ^a ± 0.25 (300)	4.33 ^b ± 0.29 (146)	3.29 ^{b±} 0.30 (127)
2014-2018	15.70 ^d ± 0.22 (163)	6.06 ^b ± 0.44 (39)	3.68 ^{acd} ± 0.42 (28)	2.84 ^a ± 0.44 (20)
Season	**	*	*	*
Main	13.94 ^a ± 0.06 (1572)	6.23 ^b ± 0.09 (1161)	4.18 ^b ± 0.09 (899)	3.03 ^a ± 0.10 (750)
Off	15.33 ^b ± 0.12 (714)	5.29 ^a ± 0.19 (417)	3.44 ^a ± 0.18 (304)	3.56 ^b ± 0.19 (269)
Type of birth	NS	NS	NS	NS
Single	14.31 ± 0.05 (2257)	5.95 ± 0.09 (1569)	3.87 ± 0.08 (1200)	3.23 ± 0.09 (1016)
Twin	16.28 ± 0.34 (29)	4.22 ± 0.75 (9)	4.69 ± 1.10 (3)	3.51 ± 1.05 (3)
Parity	NS	NS	NS	NS
1	14.56 ± 0.11 (786)	5.64 ± 0.17 (564)	3.79 ± 0.15 (435)	3.23 ± 0.18 (351)
2	14.43 ± 0.13 (594)	5.90 ± 0.17 (405)	3.76 ± 0.18 (311)	3.37 ± 0.19 (268)
3	14.66 ± 0.12 (440)	5.98 ± 0.20 (328)	3.68 ± 0.18 (266)	3.20 ± 0.18 (232)
4 and above	14.57 ± 0.15 (466)	5.82 ± 0.23 (280)	4.39 ± 0.21 (191)	3.13 ± 0.22 (168)
Body weight of dam at lambing	*	**	**	NS

** P<0.01; *P<0.05; NS – Not significant; Subclass means with dissimilar superscripts are significantly different from each other; Figure in parenthesis indicates number of observations.

Kleiber Ratio (KR)

The least-squares means for KR1, KR2, KR3, and KR4 were 14.55, 5.84, 3.90, and 3.23, respectively. The peak KR was seen in the pre-weaning phase, with KR values declining as age increased, signifying diminished feed conversion efficiency in older lambs. Comparable age-related reductions in KR have been seen in Mecheri (Jeichitra and Rajendran, 2014),

Deccani (Kumar et al., 2017), and Avikalin sheep (Mahala et al., 2019).

The dam's body weight at lambing had a considerable impact on KR1–KR3, but not on KR4. Heavier moms yielded heavier lambs with superior growth, presumably due to increased uterine space and nutritional availability (Chopra et al., 2010). The birth time substantially influenced all KR features, indicating genetic

advancement, enhanced management practices, and environmental fluctuations over the decades. Similar results have been documented in Sanjabi (Mohammadi et al., 2010), Arman (Mokhtari et al., 2013), Mecheri (Jeichitra and Rajendran, 2014), Nellore (Satish Kumar et al., 2017), and Avikalin sheep (Mahala et al., 2019). Recent observations in Dorper and Harnali sheep indicated that genetic and phenotypic variance in KR mirrored temporal alterations in breeding techniques and climatic conditions (Besufkad et al., 2024; Dash et al., 2025). Sex, parity, and birth type did not significantly affect any KR trait.

Season significantly influenced all KR traits. Lambs born in the off-season exhibited higher KR during the pre-weaning and 9–12 month periods, while main-season lambs showed superior KR during 3–6 and 6–9 months. Seasonal differences in pasture quality and availability during pregnancy and post-weaning growth are the most likely causes. The higher resource availability per lamb during the off-season also contributes to improved pre-weaning KR. The findings align with previous reports on Mecheri (Jeichitra and Rajendran, 2014), Nellore (Satish Kumar et al., 2017), Deccani (Kumar et al., 2017), and Avikalin breeds (Mahala et al., 2019). Conversely, Prakash et al. (2012) found no significant seasonal effects on post-weaning KR in Malpura sheep.

Conclusion

The computed least-squares means for ADG and KR features across various age intervals closely aligned with previously documented breed standards for Mecheri sheep. Growth performance reached its zenith during the pre-weaning phase and then diminished in the post-weaning stages, signifying a fall in both growth rate and feed conversion efficiency with increasing age. Therefore, to optimise economic benefits, selection should ideally focus on a younger age — preferably prior to weaning.

Moreover, administering additional nutrients throughout post-weaning growth stages is crucial for maintaining performance. The impact of environmental variables on growth efficiency features intensified with age, with specific elements having a more pronounced effect during early development, others gaining significance later in life, and some maintaining relevance throughout the animal's lifespan. The results unequivocally indicate that non-genetic factors are crucial in influencing the growth and development of Mecheri sheep. Consequently, meticulous evaluation of substantial environmental factors and the execution of effective flock management tactics are essential for attaining optimal productivity. Furthermore, implementing suitable adjustments for these environmental influences is essential to improve the precision of direct selection for lamb body weight and to expedite genetic advancement in this breed.

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